

Iridoid glucosides and anthraquinone from the aerial parts of *Saprosma fragrans*

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Abstract : Paederoside, paederosidic acid, 1,3-dimethoxyanthraquinone-2-carboxylic acid and β -sitosterol-D-glucoside have been isolated from the ethanolic extract of the aerial parts of *Saprosma fragrans* and their structures were established by spectral evidences and chemical studies. This is the first report of iridoid glucosides, paederoside and paederosidic acid containing rarely encountered S-methyl thiocarbonate moiety, 1,3-dimethoxyanthraquinone-2-carboxylic acid and β -sitosterol-D-glucoside in *S. fragrans*. The identities of isolated iridoid glucosides were also verified by detailed spectral data (UV, IR, FAB-MS, ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR) analyses of acetate derivatives of paederoside and paederosidic acid prepared by the acetylation of the respective iridoid glucosides.

Keywords : *Saprosma fragrans*, Rubiaceae, iridoid glucoside, paederoside, paederosidic acid, 1,3-dimethoxyanthraquinone-2-carboxylic acid, β -sitosterol-D-glucoside.

Introduction

The plant *Saprosma fragrans* (Bedd.) (Family : Rubiaceae) is a foetid erect shrubs¹. Literature survey revealed that no biological and chemical work has been carried out on this plant. In our ongoing programme for the development of new therapeutic agents from traditional medicinal plants^{2,3} and identification of the plant constituents^{4,5}, recently, we have reported the novel antifungal anthraquinones from this plant³. Here, we report the isolation and characterizations of the rarely occurring iridoid glucosides containing S-methyl thiocarbonate moiety, paederoside (1)^{6,10} and paederosidic acid⁸⁻¹⁰ (2) from the aerial parts of *S. fragrans* along with spectral data of (UV, IR, FAB-MS, ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR) of acetate derivatives 3 and 4 obtained by the acetylation of paederoside (1) and paederosidic acid (2) with acetic anhydride and dry pyridine. This is the first report of the occurrence of iridoid glucosides 1 and 2 in *S. fragrans*. Compounds, 1,3-dimethoxyanthraquinone-2-carboxylic acid¹¹ (5) and commonly encountered β -sitosterol-D-glucoside^{12,14} (6) were also isolated first time from the aerial parts of *S. fragrans*. The identities of these compounds were confirmed by comparisons of their physical and spectral data with those reported in the literature. The struc-

tures of compounds 1 and 2 were also confirmed by detailed spectral data analysis of their respective acetate derivatives 3 and 4.

Results and discussion

Chromatographic resolution of the *n*-butanol and chloroform fraction obtained from the ethanolic extract of the aerial part of *S. fragrans* yielded iridoid glucosides, paederoside (1), paederosidic acid (2), 1,3-dimethoxyanthraquinone-2-carboxylic acid (5) and β -sitosterol-D-glucoside (6) which were identified by the comparison of their physical and spectral data with those reported in the literature values. The presence of thiocarbonate group in 1 and 2 were also verified by a set of reaction (Experimental section) in which $(\text{CH}_3\text{S})_2\text{Hg}$ was formed instead of $(\text{CH}_3\text{COS})_2\text{Hg}$. Mercury salt of thioacetic acid is formed, if compounds 1 and 2 having thioacetate moiety. The characterizations of the iridoid glucosides 1 and 2 were further verified by the spectral data analyses (^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR), UV, IR and FAB-MS of acetate derivatives 3 and 4.

Experimental

Plant material : The aerial parts of *Saprosma fragrans* were collected from Kerala (Silent Valley), India and

identified by Dr. B. N. Mehrotra, Head, Botany Division, CDRI, Lucknow, India. A specimen sample is preserved in the Department.

Extraction and isolation : Air dried aerial parts (10 kg) were pulverized and extracted with 95% ethanol (4 × 15 litre) for 24 h at room temperature. The whole extract was concentrated under reduced pressure by using rotatory evaporator at 50 °C. The ethanolic extract was finally dried under *vacuo* to give solid mass (D002, 315 g). The crude ethanolic extract (D002, 145 g) was extracted with *n*-hexane. The insoluble residue was then suspended in water and partitioned with chloroform and *n*-butanol in succession to give chloroform and *n*-butanol fractions, these fractions were evaporated in rotatory evaporator and dried under *vacuo* to furnish solid mass F004 (40 g) and F005 (63 g) respectively. *n*-Butanol fraction (F005, 31 g) was chromatographed over silica gel (60–120 mesh) column eluting with polar gradient of ethyl acetate and methanol and collected eluants were monitored by TLC. On eluting the column with ethyl acetate : methanol (4 : 1 v/v) yielded fraction F0025 (20 g). The fraction F0025 (5 g) was further subjected to flash chromatography over silica gel (230–400 mesh) column eluting with chloroform and increasing amount of methanol. The eluants from chloroform : methanol (17 : 3 v/v) and chloroform : methanol (3 : 1 v/v) afforded paederoside^{8–10} (165 mg) (**1**) as a colorless amorphous powder and paederosidic acid^{8–10} (50 mg) (**2**) as a colorless amorphous powder. Chloroform fraction F004 (15 g) was chromatographed over silica gel (60–120 mesh) column eluting with *n*-hexane and increasing amount of acetone. The eluants from *n*-hexane : acetone (15 : 5 v/v) and *n*-hexane : acetone (1 : 1 v/v) gave fractions F008 (7.35 g) and F009 (4.8 g). Fraction F008 (7.0 g) was further rechromatographed over silica gel (60–120 mesh) column eluting with benzene to give eluant which on evaporation followed by crystallizations in methanol acetone mixture to give 1,3-dimethoxyanthraquinone-2-carboxylic acid¹¹ (60 mg) (**5**) as yellowish granules, m.p. 243 °C and column chromatography of the fraction F009 (4.5 g) over silica gel (60–120 mesh) column using gradient elution with benzene and methanol. The eluant from benzene : methanol (9 : 1 v/v) to give β-sitosterol-D-glucoside^{12–14} (300 mg) (**6**) as colorless granules, m.p. 278–279 °C on crystallizations with chloroform methanol mixture.

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Reaction for ascertaining the (thiocarbonate group (CH₃SCO-)) :

Compounds **1** and **2** (10 mg each) were separately placed in a round bottomed flask containing 1.5 ml of 10% Ba(OH)₂ solution and kept it for 18 h at room temperature, the flask was then connected to a trap containing 2 ml of 0.2% aqueous Hg(CN)₂ solution. The reaction mixture was acidify with dilute H₂SO₄ and nitrogen was passed through it. The colorless precipitates (3 mg for **1** and 2.8 mg for **2**) were formed in the trap which were identified as (CH₃S)₂Hg, m.p. 171.6 °C by direct comparisons (m.p. and mixed m.p.) with authentic sample. This salt was stable and liberated CH₃SH upon addition of dil. HCl, in contrast mercury salt of thioacetic acid darken immediately in air⁶.

Acetylation of compounds 1 and 2 :

Compounds **1** and **2** (20 mg each) were separately acetylated with acetic anhydride and dry pyridine (2 ml each). The reaction mixture was left for 16 h at room temperature. After usual workup of the reaction mixture gave respective acetylated products **3** (21.8 mg) as colorless needles and **4** (25 mg) as a colorless amorphous powder.

Compd.	R	Compd.	R	5
1	H	2	H	
3	CH ₃ CO	4	CH ₃ CO	

Compound 3 : Colorless needles, m.p. 154–155 °C; UV λ_{max} (MeOH) (log ε) nm : 235, 270, 285; IR ν_{max} (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 2949, 1761, 1725, 1635, 1598, 1434, 1226, 1140, 980; FAB-MS (+ve) *m/z* : 637 [M+Na]⁺, 615 [M+H]⁺, 546 [M+Na-OOCSCCH₃]⁺, 331 [tetraacetyl glucosyl moiety]⁺; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 200 MHz) δ : 5.49

(1H, d, *J* 6.2 Hz, H-1), 7.23 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, H-3), 3.74 (1H, m, H-5), 4.16 (1H, dd, *J* 2, 6.6 Hz, H-6), 5.73 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, H-7), 3.49 (1H, m, H-9), 4.32 (1H, d, *J* 12.2 Hz, H-10), 4.34 (1H, d, *J* 12.2 Hz, H-10), 4.78 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, H-1'), 5.25–4.92 (6H, m, H-2', H-3', H-4', H-5', H-6'), 1.99, 2.01, 2.03 and 2.11 (3H, each, s, 4 × CH₃CO), 2.34 (3H, s, CH₃SCOO); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 50 MHz) δ : 91.97 (C-1), 148.12 (C-3), 109.98 (C-4), 43.79 (C-5), 84.24 (C-6), 130.17 (C-7), 141.17 (C-8), 36.46 (C-9), 63.29 (C-10), 169.54 (C-11), 170.92 (C-12), 13.87 (C-13), 96.4 (C-1'), 72.61 (C-2'), 70.88 (C-3'), 68.52 (C-4'), 72.71 (C-5'), 62.10 (C-6'), 169.66 (CH₃CO), 169.75 (CH₃CO), 170.39 (CH₃CO), 171.70 (CH₃CO), 21.08, 21.05, 21.05, 20.91 (4 × CH₃CO).

Compound 4 : Colorless amorphous powder, UV λ_{max} (MeOH) (log ε) nm : 232, 208; IR ν_{max} (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 2953, 1725, 1637, 1226, 1125, 986; FAB-MS (+ve) *m/z* : 697 [M+Na]⁺, 583 [M+Na-OOCSCCH₃]⁺, 331 [tetraacetyl glucosyl moiety]⁺; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 200 MHz) δ : 5.74 (1H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz, H-1), 7.65 (1H, d, *J* 1.2 Hz, H-3), 3.72 (1H, m, H-5), 4.21 (1H, dd, *J* 2, 5.8 Hz, H-6), 6.12 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, H-7), 3.24 (1H, m, H-9), 4.84 (1H, d, *J* 15 Hz, H-10), 4.80 (1H, d, *J* 15 Hz, H-10), 4.95 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, H-1'), 5.25–4.93 (6H, m, H-2', H-3', H-4', H-5', H-6' overlapped with anomeric proton), 1.96, 2.02, 2.03 (3H, each, s, 3 × CH₃CO), 2.06 (6H, s, 2 × CH₃CO), 2.36 (3H, s, CH₃SCOO); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 50 MHz) δ : 98.17 (C-1), 155.16 (C-3), 106.44 (C-4), 45.52 (C-5), 77.40 (C-6), 129.01 (C-7), 146.54 (C-8), 38.95 (C-9), 62.02 (C-10), 169.71 (C-11), 170.24 (C-12), 13.84 (C-13), 100.72 (C-1'), 72.84 (C-2'), 71.28 (C-3'), 68.68 (C-4'), 72.52 (C-5'), 64.81 (C-6'), 169.58 (2 × CH₃CO), 170.92 (CH₃CO), 171.48 (CH₃CO), 170.57 (CH₃CO), 21.0 (2 × CH₃CO), 21.42 (2 × CH₃CO), 20.94 (CH₃CO).

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